

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

TEACHERS' PERCEPTIONS OF FORMING LINGUOCULTURAL COMPETENCE OF SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS USING MULTIMEDIA TECHNOLOGIES

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Abstract

The article is devoted to the actual problem of the formation of linguocultural competence in the context of informatization. The author analyzes the prerequisites for the demand for this competence in the light of the modern educational paradigm. However, the analysis of the scientific literature on this problem shows that it's necessary to implement different approaches (technologies) in order to develop this competence. Further, the author emphasizes that multimedia technologies can fulfill the needs of the individual in the process of forming linguocultural competence. Analysis of the secondary school teachers' perceptions show that the use of multimedia technologies contribute to the best assimilation of new material and the development of acquired skills. The author provides a list of useful multimedia resources that can improve the skills and increase the level of foreign language proficiency.

Keywords: teachers' perceptions, linguocultural competence, multimedia technologies, secondary school students.

Introduction

The modern system of teaching foreign languages to students is aimed at mastering language and speech skills in sociocultural space. In schools, there is a need for a linguoculturological approach to teaching the foreign language, which is based on the idea interconnected learning of language and culture. Co-study of language and culture, the development of not only linguistic, but also communicative and cultural competence of the individual becomes the main line of teaching the foreign language for secondary schools.

Linguocultural approach in the modern language education means that in the process of teaching, "the realities of society and culture (both spiritual and material) must be comprehended by a person through language as values of being" (Arkhipova 2004, p. 34).

In the textbook "Linguoculturology, value-semantic space of the language" N.F. Alefirenko notes: "An analysis of the methodological literature made it possible to determine the linguoculturological approach as one of the most effective, which is aimed at developing and improving intercultural communication skills through the study of language as a cultural phenomenon. Since linguoculturology is a theoretical justification for the formation of a secondary linguistic personality in a didactic interpretation, communication skills necessary for teaching carriers of various national images of the world and preventing intercultural interference, a linguocultural approach in teaching foreign language is one of the conditions for mastering vocabulary that mediates intercultural communication" [6, 105].

However, there is a need in implementing possible means to master linguocultural competence. An effective means in teaching the linguo and cultural aspects are interactive programs created on the basis of multimedia technologies. These programs are effective both for accompanying classes and for independent work,

since they can present the entire language and grammatical material of the lesson in a convenient and effective way to learn from. Multimedia technology allows to combine text into a single whole, sound, graphics, animation and video. Multimedia in many ways today overlaps the possibilities of other means [2, p. 56].

However, the previous studies have shown that the goal of multimedia technologies is to ensure equal access for all participants in the educational process to educational resources and technologies aimed at mass quality education. Multimedia tools make it possible to immerse students in an atmosphere close to that which occurs during real communication with native speakers. By playing audio tracks in a foreign language, students get the opportunity to hear free foreign speech. The teacher can use different types of tasks in lessons: situational, game, problem through the use of various activities, students experience positive emotions during the lesson, which increases their interest, and, therefore, they try to solve the task, using various methods, knowledge, skills and abilities [4, p. 221].

Studies among secondary school teachers showed the trends with significant improvement on learning outcomes and formation of linguocultural competence towards English language teaching. Yet, empirical evidence on the aspects of language acquisition on the linguo and cultural aspects is still rare. The discussion on aspects of language attitudes linked to students' linguocultural competence could be generated to get a better understanding. It is hoped to reveal a new perspective in understanding the essence of linguocultural competence. Therefore, the present study aims to investigate teachers' attitudes towards formulating linguocultural competence using multimedia technologies. Specifically, this study addresses the following research questions:

1. How multimedia technologies can be important in forming linguocultural competence of secondary stage students?

2. What multimedia technologies are mostly used to develop the linguistic and cultural knowledge of students in English language teaching?

Literature review

Linguocultural competence

Linguocultural (cultural) competence - awareness of language as a form of expression of national culture, the relationship of the language and the history of the people, the national and cultural specifics of the language, knowledge of the norms of speech etiquette, culture interethnic communication.[4]

By linguoculturological competence, we mean a system of linguoculturological knowledge, skills and abilities that students master in English lessons. The formation of this competence is considered in the works of D.I. Bashurina, A.V. Getmanskaya, E.A. Ivanova, F.S. Kebekova, M.S. Kiseleva, E.E. Makarova, M.A. Mignenko, I.A. Orekhova, M.A. Pakhnotskaya, L.G. Sayakhova, N.A. Fomenko, F.B. Khubieva, E.A. Chubina, A.M. Shuraleva and others. Researchers V.I. Teliia (2002, p. 309) and E.A. Dortman (2012, p. 26) define LCC as the ability to understand the cultural and national mentality of the carriers language, national specifics of the language picture of the world, national-cultural component of the meaning of linguistic units expressed in the cultural semantics of linguistic signs. At the same time, I.V. Kharchenkova and V.N. Taelia indicate that LCC includes the skill interpret linguistic signs and facts in terms of cultural code. Scientists V.V. Vorobyov (2007, p.56), L.A. Koneva, D.I. Bashurin (2005, p.63), I.V. Kharchenkova agree and believe that LCC is a system of knowledge about culture and cultural values embodied in the language. Therefore, linguocultural competence involves the formation of students of the necessary knowledge of educational culturological material, possession of a minimum of general literary vocabulary, knowledge of language means (phonetic, lexical, grammatical) allowing enter into the process of communication, the construction of their life in accordance with the spiritual and moral, moral and ethical, aesthetic and creative potential deployed in the linguistic consciousness conceptual sphere of national culture. In other words, it is focused on an "activity-based approach that allows to acquire the ability to use the knowledge gained in practice during intercultural communication and international communication" (Morozkina 2006, p. 324).

Multimedia technologies

Multimedia means are a set of hardware and software tools that allow a person to communicate with a computer using a variety of natural environments: sound, video, graphics, texts, animation.[9] The majority of technical tools that enable us to convey information in a very broad sense do so by utilizing the capacity for learning provided by human senses, turning information into knowledge, and stimulating learners' cognitive processes. For educational institutions to remain relevant in the twenty-first century, multimedia technologies are viewed as essential (Selwyn & Gordan, 2003). Educators have hailed the emergence of multimedia technologies as a catalyst for improvement in conventional teaching methods, encouraging innovation and advancement of established methods (Osin, 2005).

Furthermore, promoting students' effective learning interest is one of multimedia language teaching's ultimate goals, and it can be a useful strategy for engaging students in language acquisition (Thamarana, 2015). Students now have more networking chances thanks to developments in information and communication technology, particularly the Internet and interactive multimedia. One option to connect students with subject-matter experts who can provide assistance, feedback, and advice is through technology-mediated mentoring (Kerka, 2008). The potential of multimedia in education extends beyond interaction and exploratory learning. A "Virtual Education Space" could be created by the participants in the education sector.

Research methods

This study used a qualitative research approach to uncover the views of the teachers regarding the development of linguocultural competence. Through the use of a survey questionnaire, the data were collected. The underlying essential elements that affect students' linguocultural competence were discovered through analysis of the technologies influencing students' acquisition of linguocultural competence through questionnaire items.

Participants

This study involved 15 secondary stage teachers who currently teach at secondary school as the research participants. All teachers teach in Almaty's state, private and language schools. All participants are aware of the methodology of FLE.

Table 1.

Gender	Degree	Experience	School	Class
Female-10(66.7%)	Undergraduate-7 (46.7%)	1-5 y.-13(86.7%)	Private-2(13.3%)	5-6 th -6(40%)
Male-3(20%)	Master's-8(53.3%)	5-10y.-2(13.3%)	State-8(53.3%)	7-6 th -9(60%)
Prefer not to say-2(13.3%)	doctorate	10 or more	Lang.center-5(33.3%)	9 th

Participant teachers' profiles show that most of the teachers' gender is female and most of them have master's degrees, which shows that they are aware of the methodology of FLT and its main conceptual basis. Most teachers' experiences vary from 1-5 years and they teach in state schools.

Instrument

The data were gathered by the researcher using an English-language questionnaire. Part 1 focused on revealing the effectiveness of applying multimedia technologies on creating this competence (5 items), and Part 2 indicated the types of technologies (multimedia) teachers utilize in their educational process. The total number of items was 10, and they were separated into two sections (5 items). First, a Likert scale with four response options—strongly agree (1), agree (2), disagree (3), and strongly disagree (4)—was used. The second section of the survey consisted of multiple choice questions that asked participants to suggest other kinds of effective multimedia technology.

Research Procedure

Before conducting the study, the researchers have reviewed the related literature, constructed the questionnaire, and tested the instrument's reliability. After meeting the requirements, the questionnaire was dis-

tributed to the target participants. The utmost confidentiality in all information given was also emphasized. More specifically, it was calculated to know the detailed differences in teachers' attitudes towards formation of linguocultural competence. Furthermore, exploration of key features that affected teachers' perception of English language teaching in linguocultural competence was discussed to give comprehensive pedagogical implementation.

Results

This article presents a test of the hypothesis about teachers' attitudes towards teaching English using multimedia technologies. The analysis of the responses gave the researcher an overview of teachers' understanding of multimedia technologies and, in particular, their attitude to the use of multimedia technologies in teaching English and the formation of linguocultural competence.

Research question 1

Analysis on four scales was done in order to interpret the average values of the teachers' responses to the question "How multimedia technologies can be important in forming linguocultural competence of secondary stage students?". Several questionnaire results showed teachers' attitudes by interpreting answers to the following questions:

Table 2

Participant Teachers' answers				
Questions	Strongly agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly disagree
1. "Due to the integration of world cultures and languages in the modern world, linguocultural competence has become one of the most important competences that must be formed in a person"	6 (40%)	6 (40%)	3(20%)	-
2. Teachers should incorporate exercises for the formation of linguocultural competence in their lessons	7 (46.7%)	6(40%)	2(13.3%)	-
3. It is important to use multimedia technologies(presentations, audio/video materials, visuals) in English classes	12(80%)	2(13.3%)	1 (6.7%)	-

It's possible to formulate linguocultural competence using multimedia technologies

15 responses

Figure 1

Teachers' responses on the importance of formulating linguocultural competence using multimedia technologies.

Participants' answers' analysis in Table 2 showed mostly "strongly agree" and "agree" responses, that lin-

guocultural competence should be developed in the educational process and this can be successful by using special educational technologies, in particular, multimedia. Figure 1 indicates that it is relevant to formulate linguocultural competence using multimedia technologies.

In general, instructors' attitudes toward the development of linguocultural competence in English classes were positive. Positive dynamics were particularly evident in the cognitive and behavioral aspects.

Research question 2

Which of these multimedia tools do you use in your English classes

15 responses

Figure 2. Multimedia tools that mostly used in teachers' lessons

The results of the questionnaire indicated that 8 teachers use presentations(53.3%),7 teachers animational films(46.7%) and 6 teachers incorporate games(40%), others use audio apps (33.3%) in their

The purpose of the second questionnaire was to find out which multimedia technologies had the biggest impact on students' linguistic and cultural knowledge when teaching English.

English lessons. All of the above types of multimedia tools are used by 4 teachers(26.7%).

In order to specify what multimedia tools can be used to formulate linguocultural competence, teachers were asked the following question(Figure 3):

Figure 3. Teachers' responses on the most used multimedia tools, in order to develop linguocultural competence of secondary school students.

Figure 3 illustrates teachers' attitudes on the most used multimedia tools that can possibly formulate linguocultural competence of students. Thus, electronic boards like Padlet(8 teachers), classroomscreen(8 teachers), wordwall(7 teachers) had the best impact among other multimedia tools.

Discussion

The main purpose of this research is to study the perceptions of school teachers about the development of linguocultural competence using multimedia technology in English lessons. The formation of linguocultural competence, which contributes to the use of not only language, but also cultural norms, has become a

serious problem due to the active globalization of society. Revealing the attitude of teachers to the formation of this competence, the author can offer an additional point of view. First, the study showed that teachers have a positive attitude towards the use of multimedia technologies that contribute to the development of certain competencies, including linguocultural one. This finding supported a prior study by Arkhipova (2010) and Telman (2010) that demonstrated the importance of the teacher in developing students' proficiency in foreign languages through the use of interactive technologies. According to Diachkova (2020), students demonstrated their language skills and a favorable attitude toward

language learning more frequently in activity classes that were participatory, immersive, and engaging.

Using questionnaire items to explore cognitive and behavioral factors can help English teachers better understand how to use multimedia technology to increase students' linguocultural competence. Teachers at secondary schools suggested a variety of multimedia technologies. According to an analysis of Simunova's (2020) work, multimedia tools are useful means of developing foreign language abilities.

Throughout the study, teachers demonstrated favorable views toward the development of linguocultural competency through the use of multimedia technology. Thus, it is suggested to use Padlet, Classroom-Screen, and WordWall as learning tools to develop their foreign language proficiency.

Conclusion

The findings demonstrate teachers' perspectives on the development of linguocultural competence through the use of multimedia technology. This study emphasizes how educators have an optimistic outlook on all given aspects of studies. This indicates that developing a proficiency in a foreign language is attainable with the use of multimedia technologies. As a result, these technologies will greatly improve linguocultural proficiency.

Although the study provides a variety of multimedia tools, it is confined to statistical analysis of practical applications. Future studies are therefore encouraged to employ more sophisticated data study. Additionally, the assessment of students' linguistic and cultural ability was not included in the research. It is suggested that future studies will make the analysis on use of experimental research to offer a fuller understanding for the development of this competence using multimedia-based technologies.

References

1. Alefirenko, N. F. Linguoculturology: value-semantic space language [Electronic resource]: textbook. allowance - Electron. Dan. - Moscow: FLINTA, 2016. - 288 p. - URL: <https://booksonline.com.ua/view.php?book=134050>
2. Ashirmatova, M. Zh. Linguistic and cultural competence and competence: reflection of terms in methodological dictionaries // *Young scientist*. — 2019. - No. 43 (281). - p. 290-292. — URL: <https://moluch.ru/archive/281/63380/> (date of access: 05/17/2021).
3. Bubnova I.A., Krasnykh V.V. Man and his image of the world as an object and subject of modern integrative research: traditions and innovations // *Bulletin of the Moscow City Pedagogical University. Series Philology. language theory, language education*. - 2014. - No. 4 (16). - P. 80-88.
4. Byram M. *Cultural Studies in Foreign Language Education*. Toronto: Multilingual Matters, 1989. \$135 (Multilingual Matters, No 46).
5. Chalikova A.T. Scientific and theoretical foundations for the formation of intercultural and com-

municative competence in the context of informatization of foreign language education. Dissertation for the degree of Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences. Almaty, 2009. - 272p.

6. Garifullina N.L. The skill of the teacher - his competence [Electronic resource] // *Actual problems of fundamentalization of education - Cheboksary: CNS "Interactive Plus"*. Access mode: <https://doi.org/10.21661/r112642> (accessed: 05/18/2021). doi:10.21661/r-112642
7. Karasik V.I. Common sense as a linguocultural concept // *Conceptual space of language: coll. scientific papers / Ed. E.S. Kubryakova*. - Tambov, 2005. - S. 184-203.
8. Kazakhstan dated October 31, 2018 No. 604 <https://adilet.zan.kz/rus/docs/V1800017669#z1554>
9. Khlyzova N.Yu. Multimedia and their possibilities in organizing the process of teaching English to students [Text] / N.Yu. Khlyzova // *Pedagogical theory, experiment, practice / ed. T.A. Stefanovskaya*. - Irkutsk: Irkut Publishing House. IPKRO, 2018. - S. 288-295.
10. Khrolenko, A.T. *Fundamentals of cultural linguistics / A.T. Khrolenko*. - M.: Flinta, 2009. - 184 p.
11. Kodzhaspirova G.M., Kodzhaspirov A.Yu. *Pedagogical Dictionary: For students, higher and avg. ped. textbook establishments*. - M.: I; M.: Publishing Center "Academy", 2000.- 176 p.
12. Kunesbayeva K.T. New paradigms for improving education: based on the formation of professional competence of a foreign language teacher. // *Bulletin of the Kazakh National Women's Pedagogical University*. 2019 - No. 1 - P.162-168.
13. Kunanbaeva S.S. *Theory and practice of modern foreign language education*. - Almaty, 2010 - 344 p.
14. Maslova, V.A. *Cultural Linguistics / V.A. Maslova*. - M.: Academy, 2010. - 208 p.
15. Osin A.V. *Multimedia in education: the context of informatization [Text] / A.V. Osin*. - M.: Publishing service, 2005. - 320 p.
16. Popov R.F. The use of multimedia tools within the framework of a specialized English language course in a pedagogical university / R.F. Popov [Electronic resource]. - Access mode: www.ito.edu.ru/index.html
17. Potapova R.K. *New information technologies and linguistics [Text]: textbook. allowance. Ed. 6th / R.K. Potapova; Moscow state. linguistic un-t.* - M.: LENAND, 2016. - 364 p.
18. Robert I.V. Influence of tendencies of informatization, mass, global communication of modern society on vocational education [Text] / I.V. Robert // *Scientific Notes of the IIO RAO*. - 2004. - Issue. 12. - P. 3-14.
19. Robert I.V. Implementation of the possibilities of "multimedia" technology in education [Text] / I.V. Robert // *Scientific Notes of the IIO RAO*. - 2003. - Issue. 9. - P. 93-104.
20. Safonova V.V. *Cultural studies in the system of modern language education // Foreign languages at school*. 2001. No. 3. S. 17-24.